

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CREATIVE COMPETENCE

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the issue of organizing independent activities of students in professional education institutions. The author examines the issues of organizing independent activities of students, the tasks that teachers must solve in the process of independent activities of students, analyzes the views of various authors, lists the most common types of independent activities of students in professional education, reveals the importance of independent activities in forming professional skills of future specialists, and suggests focusing on the problems that currently exist in this area.*

Keywords: *creativity, independent creative activity, technology, formation, competencies, ability to solve problems independently, creativity, reproduction, heuristic approach.*

Introduction

A feature of the current stage of scientific knowledge development is the growing interest in the problem of creativity as an element of creativity, due to its role in the formation of a multifaceted personality capable of producing a large number of new ideas. Many countries around the world are concerned about the problem of creativity and the search for ways to develop it in the lifelong education system. According to K. Robinson, creativity is not a whim, a luxury, or an abstraction, but a necessity dictated by the times. Therefore, the main task of a teacher is to help a student become a free, creative, and independent individual. The problem of creativity is the subject of active research related to the processes of self-improvement and self-realization.

Creativity is a level of creative talent and ability to create that constitutes a relatively stable characteristic of an individual. Creativity is understood as an internal potential and ability to create (N. Rogers, N.Yu. Khryashcheva, S.I. Makshanov, A.J. Cropley). The word "creativity" comes from the Latin "creare," which means to generate, create, and from the English "creative," which means creative and productive. This potential is revealed and developed through students' independent activities. Currently, independent work is becoming the leading form of organizing the educational process, and this raises the issue of its activation. However, the activation of independent work does not simply involve increasing its volume in terms of time, but rather aims to enhance its effectiveness while saving students' time and effort [13].

The problem of organizing students' independent activities in the learning process is one of the most pressing issues in modern pedagogy. The current situation requires a reevaluation, correction, and new pedagogical solutions for the established methods and forms of designing and implementing students' independent work. The goals and objectives of education are currently changing, with a shift from "knowledge acquisition" to "competence development" and a focus on a person-centered approach.

The relevance of the problem of students mastering methods of independent cognitive activity is also dictated by the fact that during the learning period, the foundations of professionalism are laid and the skills of independent professional activity are formed. Modern society needs specialists who can quickly make unconventional decisions, act creatively and

independently, and contribute to the development of a particular industry. Independent work is a form of educational and cognitive activity that demonstrates a student's organizational skills, determination, creativity, and responsibility.

Independent student activities contribute to the development of initiative, discipline, accuracy, and a sense of responsibility, which are essential for future professionals in their professional activities. Independent activity of students is considered as purposeful self-organized, self-managed activity, structured by the student himself, built on deep internal motives. In modern conditions, the ability of a student to independent activity acquires a qualitatively new meaning, which is determined by the readiness of a university graduate to quickly adapt to practical professional activity in intensively changing conditions.

The fact that independent work of a student is the main way of educating independence and developing professional competence, today no one doubts. Independent activity is such work that is carried out without the direct participation of the teacher, but on his assignment, in a specially provided time for this, while students consciously strive to achieve the set goals, using their efforts and expressing in one or another form the result of mental or physical (or both) actions.

It is through independent work that a high culture of mental labor is developed. In the process of such work, the individual abilities, inclinations, and interests of students are most fully revealed, which contribute to the development of the ability to analyze facts and phenomena, and teach independent thinking, which leads to creative development and the creation of one's own opinions, views, and positions. A theoretical analysis of pedagogical literature shows that many researchers (N.G. Dair, B.P. Esipov, G.E. Kovaleva, L.M. Pimenova, L.A. Ponomarev, and others) identify independence as a personality trait that serves as the foundation for this approach.

The problems of independent work of a student at a university are covered in scientific and methodological literature. These problems are studied by G.S. Zakirov, V.D. Zemzyulina, E.V. Zakharova, and I. Kovalevsky. However, unfortunately, this literature does not yet provide sufficient coverage of the problems and features of independent work of a student in the context of implementing a multi-level training and education system in university life. Let's take a closer look at the concept of "independent work." According to a modern dictionary on pedagogy, independence is defined as the ability to set a specific goal, persistently pursue it on one's own, take responsibility for one's actions, and act consciously and proactively, not only in familiar situations but also in new circumstances that require unconventional solutions. Independence is not innate; it develops as a person matures and has its own characteristics at each age stage.

In this regard, the idea of N.G. Dair is interesting, who notes: "... it is necessary to see the emergence of independence, its development, the stages of its complexity, and to correlate the stages of complexity of various types of independent work with this". In our opinion, the above statement contains a fruitful idea about the stages of independence demonstrated by students when performing less complex and more complex types of independent work. I. Zinoviev notes that in higher education, the concept of independence is associated with the idea of freedom in choosing the ways and means of solving the problems that a person faces. This means that students should perform independent work without guidance or assistance from university professors. However, it should be noted that excessive independence can reduce the effectiveness of the student's independent work. There is also a view of independent work that equates it with self-education, substitutes it, and therefore loses its specific features.

It is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of "independent work" and "self-education." Self-education is a system of continuous knowledge acquisition, which goes beyond

the scope of academic work at a university. However, the objectives of self-education are much broader than those of independent work. Self-education, unlike independent work, is not only a form of acquiring, deepening, and acquiring new knowledge during university studies, but also a form of continuing education for young professionals after graduation. Consequently, the concept of "independent work" and the concept of "self-education" have different meanings. Mixing these concepts leads to confusion in the choice of means, forms, and methods of their practical implementation. In our opinion, independent work should be understood only as an integral part of self-education, which has broader goals.

Some scientists consider independent work as a means of developing generalized skills, cognitive independence, creative activity, and personality socialization, and associate it with the ability to self-organize. Independent work is defined by some authors as a teaching method; by others, as a learning technique; and by still others, as a form of organizing educational activities. It should be noted that the most complete definition of independent work is given by V.I. Andreev [6]. His point of view is based on the fact that a wide variety of teaching methods and techniques can be used in the process of independent work, and therefore, in his opinion, it is incorrect to use the term "method" as a generic term for independent work. He also believes that the term "means" is not the main term, but rather an auxiliary or specific feature, and cannot be used as a generic term.

Thus, independent work of students is a form of organizing their educational activities, carried out under the direct or indirect supervision of a teacher, during which students perform various types of tasks predominantly or completely independently in order to develop their knowledge, skills, and personal qualities. Independent work is a type of educational activity that involves a certain level of student independence in all its structural components: from setting the problem to carrying out control, self-control, and correction, with a dialectical transition from performing the simplest types of work to more complex, search-oriented tasks, and a constant transformation of the guiding function of pedagogical management into forms of orientation and correction, with a gradual transfer of all functions to the student. I believe that this approach is in line with the reality and nature of independent work.

Independent work in the modern educational process is considered as a form of organization of learning, which is able to provide independent search for the necessary information, creative perception and comprehension of the educational material during classroom activities, various forms of cognitive activity of students in classes and during out-of-class time, development of analytical abilities, skills of control and planning of study time, development of skills and abilities of rational organization of study work.

A survey of students aimed at self-improvement revealed several problems faced by students. It was found that 18% of students have difficulty in allocating their time, 60% of students noted that they do not have enough time, and 15% of students complained about difficulties in completing independent work. This indicates that the main problem is a lack of time. To understand the reality, let's try to calculate the student's time. Students usually have 3-4 classes per day (from 8:30 a.m. to 3:30 p.m.), followed by consultations (1-2 more hours), which means that they leave the institute at 4-5 p.m. Many students take about an hour to get to their place of residence. They can also allocate two more hours for rest and meals. Therefore, by 7-8 p.m., students can start their independent work at home. Many students have various household duties that also take up time. After a busy day, students may experience fatigue, exhaustion, and so on. Therefore, it can be concluded that only the most energetic and healthy students will be able to

engage in independent work at home. However, there are usually only a few such students. The remaining students will need more time to recover their energy. So, how can we find a solution to this problem? There are two main approaches to independent student work:

- The first is to increase the role of independent work in the classroom. This requires teachers to develop methods and forms of classroom organization that can ensure a high level of student independence and improve the quality of education;

- The second is to increase students' activity in all areas of independent work during extracurricular time. However, as mentioned above, this is associated with several difficulties, primarily due to the unpreparedness of both students and teachers. Students do not attend consultations assigned by teachers, leaving the work on control and course assignments for the end of the semester. Additionally, the existing methodological support for control and course assignments is insufficient for effectively organizing independent work.

It should be noted that the ineffectiveness and slowness of extracurricular independent work is caused by the teacher's insufficiently clear organization of students' cognitive activity in extracurricular independent work. Often, the teacher does not focus students on mastering the basic knowledge and skills, does not select the educational material for the assignment clearly enough, and includes extensive assignments in extracurricular independent work that must be completed within a short timeframe. All of these issues reduce the effectiveness of independent work and lower students' cognitive motivation.

Methodology

The traditional learning system is not always able to develop a person's creativity, as it is based on memorizing information and accumulating facts. In most cases, the creative aspects of a person's personality are suppressed in everyday life. Therefore, the development of creativity can only be achieved in a specially organized environment, and it is necessary to introduce special independent tasks into the learning process that allow for the development of creative thinking, creativity, and the further use of creative abilities. The development of creativity is individual for each student, so it is advisable to prepare differentiated tasks.

To develop creative thinking means to form and improve mental operations: analysis, synthesis, comparison and generalization, classification, planning, abstraction, and to have such characteristics of thinking as criticality, depth, flexibility, breadth, speed, variability, and to develop imagination and to have knowledge of different content. To form creativity as a personal, and not only behavioral property, a specially organized environment is required. The so-called "local" methods of developing creativity (for example, solving non-standard problems) are certainly useful.

However, because of their application, students simply learn some new ways of solving problems and subsequently reproduce the actions they have learned (for example, teams that participate in intellectual competitions are specially trained). In such cases, creativity is manifested in response to external influences and in certain circumstances, rather than as a result of the individual's personal needs. Therefore, in order to develop creativity as a personal trait, a special environment is needed that provides a multifaceted and systematic impact on the student. Independent work is mandatory for the development of creativity, and it is determined by the curriculum. In the structure of educational activities, it takes up from a third to two-thirds of the total study time. The organization of independent work is systematic throughout the entire period

of student education. An important aspect of independent work is that it not only solves educational tasks, but also addresses the issue of self-development and self-improvement for the student.

In the modern educational process, the student is not just a consumer of information, but a creative seeker of knowledge. At the same time, the teacher's task is not only to transfer information in a ready-made form, but also to encourage the student to engage in independent cognitive activity, to form the skills of independence in obtaining knowledge, as this is necessary for professional activity and career growth.

There are general principles for organizing independent work:

— the principle of interactive learning (providing an interactive dialogue and feedback that allows for control and correction of the student's actions);

— the principle of developing a student's intellectual potential (forming algorithmic, visual-figurative, and theoretical thinking styles, the ability to make optimal or varieties decisions in a complex situation, and the ability to process information);

— the principle of ensuring the integrity and continuity of the didactic learning cycle (providing the opportunity to complete all parts of the didactic cycle within a topic, section, or module).

There are also specific principles for organizing independent work for university students:

- the principle of individualized learning, which is manifested in the teacher's consideration of the student's individual psychological characteristics when providing pedagogical support for independent work;

- the principle of regulation of education, which reflects the need to choose a learning strategy and plan the organization of students' independent work (including methodological developments for students' independent work);

- the principle of relying on basic knowledge and skills, which requires students to have minimal technical skills and the ability to use their free time effectively for independent work;

- the principle of advanced learning, which ensures that independent work is focused on activating and developing the student's cognitive abilities, as well as on developing the ability to independently predict, choose, and solve didactic problems, and acquire knowledge in collaboration with other students studying the same discipline or course;

- the principle of feedback, which allows participants to discuss and correct problematic issues in a given discipline or course in a timely manner;

- the principle of external control and self-assessment, which includes the exchange of information not only with the teacher, but also with other students studying the same discipline or course;

- the principle of scientificity, which allows participants to independently solve the assigned tasks at the current level of scientific knowledge;

- the principle of visibility, which involves presenting information in an accessible form;

- the principle of linking theory with practice, which makes it possible to solve situational problems;

- the principle of accessibility and feasibility of independent work;

- the principle of taking into account the complexity of academic disciplines and the optimal planning of independent work;

Practice shows that students differ in their level of readiness to implement the requirements for independent work. There are two main groups of students:

- the first is characterized by the fact that its representatives are focused on completing independent work tasks and possess universal educational competencies that allow them to successfully meet the requirements for completing independent work (the ability to understand and remember acquired information, think logically, reproduce material in writing and orally, conduct measurements, calculations, and design).

- students in the second group do not have a stable orientation towards continuous independent work when mastering educational material, and they have a low level of development of universal educational competencies and self-organization skills.

Given this situation, the teacher should develop differentiated tasks that differ in complexity when organizing independent student activities. To do this, it is necessary to study the students' capabilities and, based on the results, divide the students into groups based on their readiness for independent activities. Then, for each group, develop a specific development program and a set of tasks for independent activities. This approach will optimize the process and increase the effectiveness of independent activities.

Independent student work can be organized at different levels, depending on the didactic goals and the students' level of preparedness:

1. Independent work based on a sample or reproductive independent work — low level of independence. require the transfer of a known solution method directly into a similar or remotely similar intra-subject situation. These works are performed on the basis of "specific algorithms" previously demonstrated by the teacher and tested by students when performing previous tasks, thus, performing independent work of this type, students make a direct transfer of a known method into a similar intra-subject situation. In this case, all the student's actions are aimed at mastering a set of independent activities. The fundamental possibility of mastering independent work methods stems from the similarity of the conditions of this task and previously known tasks (from the similarity of the subject area and the relationships between objects), and the appropriateness of using the corresponding methods either stems from the conditions of the task or is determined by the teacher's instructions. Thus, reproducing independent work contributes to the formation of skills and abilities, as well as the memorization of independent work methods in specific situations.

2. Independent work of the reconstructive-varieties type is a threshold level of independence. It allows you to meaningfully transfer knowledge to typical situations, teaches you to analyze events, phenomena, and facts, creates conditions for the development of students' mental activity, and forms the methods and techniques of cognitive activity.

3. Heuristic independent work or partially search-based work is an advanced level of independence. It contributes to the formation of students' creative personalities. When performing this type of work, students constantly search for new solutions, generalize and systematize their knowledge, and apply it to completely unconventional situations.

4. In-subject and inter-subject research or creative independent work is a high level of independence. This is the highest level in the system of independent work. To perform such independent work, you must be able to transform and transfer knowledge and problem-solving methods, independently develop new problem-solving methods, determine the content, purpose, and develop a plan for solving a learning task. Independent work of this kind usually contains cognitive tasks, according to the conditions of which it is necessary: to analyze unusual situations; to identify the characteristic features of the educational problems that arise in these situations; to look for ways to solve these problems; to choose the most rational from the known ways,

modifying them in accordance with the conditions of the learning situation. Heuristic and creative independent work have great opportunities for the development of students' creativity.

Conclusions

Thus, independent work is a special means of teaching that, firstly, corresponds to a specific goal and task in each specific learning situation, secondly, forms a certain amount of creative competence in students to solve cognitive problems, thirdly, develops a psychological attitude in students to independently and systematically expand their knowledge, fourthly, is an essential tool for pedagogical guidance and management of students' independent work, and finally, is an essential condition for self-organization and self-discipline in students' cognitive activities. Solving the problems of forming a creative personality of a graduate, capable of self-development, self-education, independent innovative activity, is impossible through the simple transfer of ready-made knowledge from the teacher to the student. It is necessary to transfer the student from the position of a passive consumer of knowledge to the position of an active subject of the educational process, participating in the formation of their competencies, able to formulate a problem, analyze ways to solve it, find the optimal result and prove their point of view.

In this context, it becomes clear that the status of independent work in the modern educational process is fundamentally changing. The increased importance of independent student work requires a fundamental reevaluation of the educational process at universities, which should be designed to foster learning skills, self-development, creativity, and various adaptations to future professional activities.

The effectiveness of independent work in the learning process largely depends on the conditions of its organization, the content and nature of the tasks, the logic of their construction, the source of knowledge, the relationship between the existing and expected knowledge in the content of the tasks, and the quality of the results achieved during this work. However, the following questions arise: What are the optimal conditions for students' independent activities? How independent should a student be in such activities? How can a differentiated approach be implemented in organizing students' independent activities? What technologies are effective in different situations? How can students' independent activities be organized to promote creativity?

To solve these problematic issues, it is necessary to approach them individually and, first of all, to find the level of independence that will give the best results and help the student's development. It is also important to study each student's capabilities and develop differentiated tasks based on their complexity. Finally, it is necessary to develop effective technologies for organizing students' independent activities. One option for implementing new technologies is the credit-based education model, which allows for the continuous updating of initial information in the form of changing examples and statistical data, as well as the modification of model parameters, which helps to better understand and enhance the effectiveness of students' independent work.

It should be noted that independent work by students is only possible if the student has a strong interest and desire to acquire knowledge. In this case, the most effective motivator is internal motivation, which comes from the activity itself. This can be seen as an interest in learning and creating conditions for the successful development of the student's intellectual skills, where the perception of new information evokes positive emotions and the activity itself encourages learning.

To work with the acquired knowledge, skills, and abilities, teachers often offer creative tasks, as they contribute to the development of the ability to use knowledge to solve relevant

practical problems. For each creative task, the teacher must develop regulatory requirements, and for certain groups of students, they must also consider the level of creative activity. If necessary, the teacher should provide guidance on how to complete these tasks. Such independent work is interesting if the tasks are novel, if they involve research using new methods of research or measurement, and if they involve active thinking or practical activities related to finding the most efficient ways to complete the tasks, analyzing the results, and writing a report.

The organization of independent work is an effective means of activating students' creative independence. Students' independence and activity are closely related, as independence is the highest form of activity that is determined by the nature and method of students' activities. The basis of students' independent work is a conscious approach to the learning process, which is the highest degree of thinking. At every stage of students' independent work, clear, timely, and effective control and verification of knowledge acquisition, as well as the level of skill development and ability enhancement, are necessary.

To ensure the effectiveness of students' independent work, it is necessary to:

- justifying the combination of classroom and independent work;
- methodologically correct organization of the student's work in the classroom and outside of it;
- providing the student with the necessary methodological materials in order to transform the process of independent work into a creative process;
- using active learning methods;
- monitoring the organization and progress of the student's independent work and taking measures to encourage the student for its high-quality performance.

The importance of students' independent work cannot be overestimated. It is only through independent completion of assignments that knowledge is consolidated. Students begin to understand the educational material, and they develop a desire to learn. The goal of students' independent work is to teach them how to work with educational material and scientific information in a meaningful and independent manner, and to instill the ability to continuously improve their qualifications. The decisive role in organizing students' independent work belongs to the teacher, who should work not with a student "in general" but with a specific individual, with their strengths and weaknesses, individual abilities, and inclinations. The teacher's task is to see and develop the best qualities of the student as a future highly qualified specialist.

A student's independent work is intended not only for mastering a specific discipline, but also for developing certain skills in educational, scientific, and professional activities, as well as the ability to take responsibility, solve problems independently, and find constructive solutions to crisis situations. Independent work is not aimed at providing knowledge. It is aimed at teaching students how to independently search for and develop creativity.

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